

**PERSONALIZED APPROACH TO PREVENTION OF
UNFAVORABLE RESULTS OF SEPTOPLASTY****Umarov Bakhtiyor Yatgarovich
Otaev Hamid Sultanovich****Director of the Children's National Medical Center,
DSc, Associate Professor, Tashkent, Uzbekistan
Plastic Surgeon at Medmorial Hospital,
Urgench, Uzbekistan
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19563653>****ARTICLE INFO**Received: 09th April 2026Accepted: 11th April 2026Online: 13th April 2026**KEYWORDS***septoplasty, functional outcomes,
nasal breathing***ABSTRACT**

Septoplasty is the main method of surgical correction of nasal septal deformities, but the variability of functional results requires a detailed analysis of the clinical characteristics of patients. It was found that the clinical characteristics of patients, including the severity of symptoms, the presence of concomitant inflammatory changes in the nasal mucosa, and individual features of the course of the disease, have a significant impact on the outcomes of surgical treatment. These differences highlight the need for a personalized approach to preoperative assessment and postoperative management of patients.

Introduction.

A personalized approach in modern medicine involves taking into account the individual biological characteristics of the patient in order to optimize treatment tactics. In the context of septoplasty, this means that patients should be stratified according to the severity of immunoinflammatory changes and risk groups for adverse outcomes should be identified[1,2]. This approach makes it possible not only to predict the results of surgical treatment, but also to justify the implementation of targeted preoperative preparation aimed at reducing the activity of allergic inflammation[3].

Materials and methods. The study was conducted with the participation of 160 patients with nasal septal deformity and nasal breathing disorders who underwent examination and surgical treatment in the period from 2022 to 2025. Depending on the chronology of work stages, patients were divided into two groups:

- the control group consisted of 78 (48.8%) patients who underwent standard methods of diagnosis and surgical treatment during 2022-2023 with parallel determination of allergological and immunological parameters without changing the standard management tactics;

- the main group consisted of 82 (51.2%) patients who, in the period from 2024-2025, used the methods developed by us for predicting and preventing adverse functional outcomes according to the treatment and diagnostic algorithm developed by us.

Results. In the early postoperative period, intergroup differences persisted. In patients with an unsatisfactory outcome, the total IgE level remained almost 2.8 times higher than in

those with a favorable outcome ($p < 0.001$), and local eosinophilia remained more than 3 times higher ($p < 0.001$). The most pronounced differences were related to mucosal inflammation, which was confirmed by a significant increase in eosinophils in nasal cytology and ENI index.

Conclusion. Thus, the developed personalized therapeutic and diagnostic approach based on preliminary stratification of patients according to the immuno-allergic risk profile using the "IAF-MS" scale makes it possible to purposefully reduce the severity of the eosinophil-associated immunoinflammatory response both in the preoperative and postoperative periods of septoplasty. The use of this algorithm does not contradict the basic principles of surgical training, but contributes to their systematization and more rational use, taking into account the individual characteristics of the patient.

References:

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